

Review Article

Impedance spectroscopy of neurons, inductors and synapses: A path to understanding brain-like computation

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This review underscores the growing relevance of impedance spectroscopy (IS) in neuromorphic research and its capacity to advance brain-inspired computation. Neuromorphic systems, which emulate biological neural networks, provide compact, adaptive, and energy-efficient solutions for edge applications such as robotics, wearable health monitoring, and environmental sensing. Since early studies on electrochemical oscillators, IS has been pivotal in probing neuron-like dynamics. Frequency-domain analysis of artificial synapses yields essential insights into synaptic plasticity—the core mechanism of learning and memory—shaped by functions like retention and filtering. Memristor-based synapses display chemical inductor behavior, evident as a negative arc in impedance spectra, highlighting their complex dynamics. More broadly, IS is increasingly positioned not only as a diagnostic tool for material performance but also as a framework for designing systems governed by ion migration, accumulation, and relaxation. By capturing these processes, IS provides a powerful perspective for analyzing and engineering physical computation components.

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Current Opinion in Electrochemistry 2025, **54**:101767

This review comes from a themed issue on **Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) (2025)**

Edited by **Mark E. Orazem**, and **Vincent Vivier**

For a complete overview see the [Issue](#) and the [Editorial](#)

Available online 10 October 2025

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coelec.2025.101767>

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Introduction

Impedance spectroscopy (IS) is a general-purpose technique for the characterization of dynamic properties of devices in the frequency domain [1]. It utilizes

the main tools of equivalent circuits and complex impedance plots [2]. This paper aims to consolidate emerging knowledge on IS as it becomes increasingly relevant to the development of next-generation computing systems.

As artificial intelligence (AI) applications continue to expand, traditional von Neumann architectures face growing limitations in terms of energy consumption, scalability, and latency. These challenges have spurred growing interest in neuromorphic and physical computing approaches—a field focused on building hardware systems inspired by the structure and function of the human brain [3–5]. The interest in neuromorphic hardware is deeply tied to the desire to replicate key biological neural properties—such as event-driven signaling, synaptic plasticity, and parallel processing—that give the brain its remarkable efficiency and adaptability [6]. Traditional computing systems struggle with bottlenecks created by the separation of memory and logic, whereas biological systems overcome this by integrating them seamlessly at the level of individual synapses and neurons.

Neuromorphic architectures seek to emulate these principles by building novel hardware that integrates sensing, memory, and computation in a unified, event-driven manner. A neuromorphic computing architecture consists of interconnected neurons and synapses, as illustrated in [Figure 1](#). Unlike traditional CMOS systems, these architectures increasingly depend on emerging materials [7], that enable the dynamic, analog-like behaviors required to emulate neural processes at the device level, like organic electrochemical transistors (OECT) that have been developed into spiking neurons [8], and memristors [9,10] which exhibit analog behavior suitable for replicating synaptic functions at the hardware level.

Neuromorphic networks are a class of brain-inspired systems that differ significantly from conventional artificial neural networks (ANNs), particularly in how they process information and how they are implemented in hardware. A key characteristic is their event-driven nature—neurons process and transmit information only when a specific threshold is reached, producing

Figure 1

Scheme of neuromorphic computation.

discrete spikes. This spiking neural network (SNN) model allows for sparse, energy-efficient computation that mirrors how biological neurons communicate.

The role of the neuron can be replicated by self-sustained oscillator devices that generate periodic signals from constant, non-periodic energy sources [11]. These systems mimic the spiking behavior of biological neurons by converting steady inputs into rhythmic outputs, similar to natural oscillatory processes observed in biology [12]. IS criteria for electrochemical self-sustained oscillators were established by the work of Koper [13,14] and this method has been used extensively [15,16]. Thus, electrochemistry provides the main experience in the characterization of neuron-like systems by IS. Recently, the impedance conditions have been outlined for a wider class of neuron-like oscillations, starting with FitzHugh-Nagumo model (FHN), and extended to various type of oscillator models [17,18].

Furthermore, the synapses regulate the transmission of signals between neurons. A synapse requires variable and stable conductance states to represent the weight of the signal. Additionally, they typically implement local learning rules, such as spike-timing-dependent plasticity (STDP), which adjusts synaptic strengths based on the precise timing of spikes, offering a more biologically plausible alternative to backpropagation used in ANNs. Key effects for learning rules are potentiation, when the weight is increased by stimulation voltage

pulses, and depression that reduces the conductance of the synapse by inhibition pulses. At the level of synapses, frequency plays a key role in determining how signals are transmitted.

In the context of neuromorphic engineering, where precise control over conductance modulation is essential, the ability of IS to quantify resistive, capacitive, and diffusive contributions across timescales makes it a uniquely powerful diagnostic technique. Table 1 summarizes the range of material platforms explored for synaptic applications. The last column highlights the extent to which IS has been employed in their study. Among these, electrolyte-gated devices—such as electric double-layer (EDL) transistors, organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs), and synaptic devices based on metal–organic frameworks (MOFs)—stand out as the clearest examples where electrochemical IS has become an indispensable tool for characterization. IS has been increasingly positioned not only as a means of validating material performance but also as a guiding framework for the rational design of electrolyte-gated synaptic systems [19–21]. In these systems, the fundamental operating principle relies on ionic transport within the electrolyte and its coupling to interfacial capacitance at the channel or electrode surface. Because the device functionality—short-term and long-term plasticity, retention, and synaptic filtering—depends strongly on the dynamics of ion migration, accumulation, and relaxation, IS provides unique access to these mechanisms in the frequency domain [22]. In OECTs,

Table 1

Comparison of artificial neural synapse device technologies.

Material/Technology	Typical Structure	Key Materials	Synaptic Properties	Potential Applications	IS Role/Usage
Polymer Electrolyte/EDL Transistors	Three-terminal transistor with electrolyte gating	Polymers (P3HT, PEDOT:PSS), ionic liquids, gels	Low-voltage operation; tunable short/long-term plasticity; analog weight states	Neuromorphic circuits, artificial sensory systems, flexible electronics	Yes – IS widely used to analyze ionic motion and capacitance modulation [19,20]
Organic Electrochemical Transistors (OECTs)	Electrolyte-gated organic transistor	PEDOT:PSS channel, aqueous electrolytes	Biocompatible; emulate short-term plasticity; stable ion–electron coupling	Bio-interfacing, brain–machine interfaces, biosensors	Yes – IS used to probe ion injection and channel impedance [24]
Molecular/MOF-based Synapses	Hybrid transistor or memristor with MOF layers	Metal–organic frameworks (Zr-MOFs, etc.), conjugated polymers	Selective memory, attention-like filtering, tunable ion transport	Artificial retina, neuroprosthetics, sensory processing	Yes – IS crucial for probing ionic transport through MOF pores [25,26]
Resistive Switching Organic Synapses	MIM structures with organic layers	Small-molecule or polymer insulators	Analog switching; simple fabrication; flexibility	Low-cost neuromorphic elements, flexible devices	Sometimes IS used to study bulk charge trapping [35]
Halide Perovskite Memristors	Sandwich device with perovskite layers	Organic and inorganic halide perovskites	Gradual and abrupt switching	Low-cost neuromorphic elements, photoactive synapses	Yes, IS amply used to obtain impedance elements and explain hysteresis [27,28]
Fluidic Nanochannels	Asymmetrical nanopores	Nanopores in Si, polymers, or 2D materials; aqueous electrolytes	Mimic synaptic plasticity via ionic flux; enable chemical selectivity and regulation; highly biomimetic	Artificial synapses, chemical sensing, biohybrid neuromorphic platforms	Yes – IS applied to analyze ion transport dynamics, channel resistance, and capacitive modulation [31–33].
Oxide Memristors (HfOx, TaOx, TiOx)	Metal–insulator–metal (MIM) crossbars	Transition metal oxides	Non-volatile switching; long-term potentiation/depression; high endurance; fast speed	In-memory computing, neuromorphic accelerators, AI hardware	Sometimes used to probe interface states and switching kinetics [36]
2D Material Synapses	Field-effect or memristor devices	MoS ₂ , graphene oxide, h-BN, black phosphorus	High flexibility, scalability; multilevel conductance; ultrathin channels	Wearable neuromorphic systems, transparent electronics	Occasionally – to characterize defect/ion dynamics, less common than polymers [37]
Ferroelectric Synapses	Ferroelectric-gated transistors or capacitors	HfZrO ₂ , P(VDF-TrFE)	Non-volatile, polarization-driven plasticity; low power	Neuromorphic logic, memory-in-logic	Rarely, but IS can probe ferroelectric switching dynamics [38]

for instance, impedance spectra provide insights into volumetric doping and the correspondent chemical (volume) capacitance, which directly influence switching speed and signal amplification [23,24]. Similarly, in MOF-based synaptic devices, IS helps elucidate ion migration pathways and dielectric properties that mimic biological plasticity [25,26]. IS also becomes a widely used tool for the analysis of ionic transport and polarization in solid mixed ionic-electronic memristors such as halide perovskites [27,28].

A fully ionic system is the fluidic nanochannels that leverage ionic motion in electrolyte solutions across the pore to emulate the operating principles of the brain [29]. Drawing inspiration from the parallel transport of diverse ionic and molecular species across biological active pores in aqueous environments, the regulation of ion flow through biomimetic nanopores enables the realization of key brain-like functionalities, including synaptic plasticity and chemical modulation [30]. In these systems, IS becomes a widely used tool to evaluate capacitances, ionic transport, and synaptical responses [31–33].

In contrast, oxide memristors and 2D material synaptic devices are most often evaluated using direct current (DC) I–V sweeps, hysteresis loops, or pulsed programming, since their switching is dominated by electronic mechanisms such as filament formation, defect migration, or charge trapping. While impedance techniques are occasionally applied in these solid-state devices, their use is less widespread compared to ion-driven architectures.

The broader importance of IS lies in its ability to deconvolute resistive, capacitive, and sometimes inductive elements of the device response, enabling the mapping of physical processes to functional behaviors reminiscent of biological synapses and neurons [27,34]. Frequency-dependent impedance can capture phenomena analogous to short-term filtering (capacitive charging), relaxation and recovery dynamics (ionic transport), and long-term adaptation (structural or electrochemical reorganization). This makes IS not only a diagnostic tool but also a bridge between the physics of artificial synapse devices and the computational strategies of the brain.

An additional and growing area is oscillator-based computing (OBC) [39]. This approach uses networks of coupled nonlinear oscillators to perform computation by exploiting their natural dynamics, synchronization patterns, and phase relationships. The collective behavior of these oscillators enables pattern recognition, temporal coding, and efficient signal processing. Oscillator-based systems are particularly promising for tasks involving temporal sequences and classification, and they share with neuromorphic hardware the goal of

achieving brain-like performance with minimal power consumption. The electrochemical oscillators have been explored for coupling systems that perform OBC [40,41].

Frequency domain analysis

Frequency analysis is particularly interesting for the study of synapses, neurons, and brain activity patterns because neuronal communication is not static—it unfolds over time through electrical signals that often vary in complex, oscillatory patterns. Selected introductory ideas about the IS properties of synapses, inductors, negative resistance and neurons are provided in the Supporting Information.

Synaptic plasticity, the process by which synaptic strength changes with experience, is sensitive to timing and frequency. Repeated stimulation at specific frequencies, as seen in protocols for inducing long-term potentiation or depression, can lead to lasting changes in synaptic efficacy. This means that understanding how synapses respond to different frequencies is key to uncovering how learning and memory occur at the cellular level. Synaptic connections can behave like filters, responding preferentially to inputs of certain frequencies. For instance, synapses and neurons may act as low-pass filters, favoring slower changes in activity, while others may be more responsive to fast or precisely timed inputs [6,42]. This frequency-dependent filtering shapes how neurons integrate signals from their many inputs and influences the overall flow of information through neural circuits.

Furthermore, frequency analysis enables researchers to go beyond traditional rate coding, where information is represented by the number of spikes, to explore how timing and rhythmic patterns of spikes encode information. Neurons may use not only the rate but also the timing and phase relationships of spikes relative to ongoing oscillations to represent and transmit information more efficiently [39,43].

Neurons don't just fire at random; they often exhibit rhythmic activity across various frequency bands such as theta, alpha, beta, and gamma. These oscillations are crucial for understanding many brain functions, including attention, memory, and sensory processing. By shifting from the time domain to the frequency domain, these rhythms can be more clearly identified, making frequency analysis a powerful tool for interpreting neural dynamics.

Finally, frequency analysis is essential in clinical and systems neuroscience. Many brain disorders, such as epilepsy, Parkinson's disease, or schizophrenia, are associated with disruptions in normal brain rhythms [44]. Tools like EEG (Electroencephalography) and MEG (Magnetoencephalography), which measure brain

activity in the frequency domain, rely on frequency analysis to interpret these patterns and potentially diagnose or monitor such conditions.

In short, frequency analysis offers a powerful method for individual neuron-like systems and a window into the dynamic language of the brain. It helps decode how neurons and synapses process time-varying signals, supports our understanding of brain rhythms and neural coding, and plays a central role in both basic neuroscience and clinical applications.

Synapses and inductors

In the context of neuromorphic applications, the crucial synaptic property is the conductance change, or resistive switching, as further explained in Supporting Information. A general class of two-contact systems denoted *memristors* [9] are amply used in brain inspired computing [45], especially in the role of synapses [46].

For specific description of synapse properties and impedance, we consider a conductance-based synapse model of the form [47,48].

$$I_{tot}(u) = [g_L + (g_H - g_L)x]u + C_m \frac{du}{dt} \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_k(u) \frac{dx}{dt} = x_{eq}(u) - x \quad (2)$$

The total current in Eq [1] includes (a) the conduction current governed by the voltage in the device u and an internal state variable x , and (b) the capacitive current associated with the capacitance C_m . The adaptation equation [2] regulates the evolution of x . This variable describes a physical quantity such as a conducting filament in memristors that builds up slowly and determines the conductance. In equilibrium, it is $x \rightarrow x_{eq}$, which is normally a sigmoidal function. The activation function passes from $x = 0$ to $x = 1$, when the voltage exceeds a threshold, causing a change of conductance from a low value g_L to a high value g_H . This type of dynamical model was first introduced in the HH system.

The model synapses like Eqs [1,2]. contains two essential features for the required dynamical behavior: rectification and hysteresis [49]. A step voltage will produce a delayed increase of the current. Therefore these equations describe a generalized (not electromagnetic) inductor mechanism [46], that has been denominated a *chemical inductor* [50]. This physical behavior has a notorious impedance response, where the effective capacitance becomes negative in some frequency domain, as further explained in Supporting Information. This feature has been observed in fluidic nanochannels as shown in Figure 2 [33,51], but more generally the inductive property occurs in an enormous

variety of systems, often involving a slow ionic step in an external electronic current, particularly in electrochemistry [52,53], sensors, biofilms [54] and photovoltaics [55]. Recently different systems have been described using the concept of a chemical inductor [56–59]. The relation between synapses potentiation and the internal chemical inductor has been well understood [46,47], and the connexion can be investigated by IS. It has been shown [60] that Eqs [1,2]. provide both a conduction inductor mechanism in the potentiation voltages, and a conduction capacitance in the depression range, as explained in Fig. 2. This association has been demonstrated experimentally in many cases [28,32,33,46].

Neurons and oscillators

At the heart of brain-inspired computation is the neuron, which encodes and transmits information via spiking signals. In oscillator-based neuromorphic systems, this function is emulated by self-sustained oscillators—devices that produce periodic signals from a constant power source [11]. Self-oscillators replicate key neuronal behavior, where information is conveyed primarily through the timing of spikes rather than their waveform, enabling robust and reliable signal transmission. Similarly, OBC [39] uses the phase relationships of oscillators to process information efficiently, offering an energy-efficient alternative to conventional computing.

A self-sustained oscillator incorporates a resonant structure, typically composed of a capacitance and a chemical inductor [6]. While a passive LC resonator can generate periodic outputs when driven by an external periodic signal, it cannot sustain oscillations on its own. To achieve self-sustained oscillations, an additional physical mechanism is required, a negative resistance that offsets the intrinsic energy losses in the circuit, allowing for continuous oscillation under constant power input. More information on the negative differential resistance (NDR) is provided in the Supporting Information.

The basic dynamical structure of self-oscillators can be observed in the Hodgkin-Huxley model (HH) [61] that is the cornerstone of neuroscience description for neuron activity [6], and in more simple neuron models like the FHN and a large variety of models with diverse properties summarized by Izhikevich [43]. Neuron dynamical models, such as those originating from the HH framework, exhibit features like rectification and hysteresis already obtained in the synapse-memristor model of Eqs. [1,2], and in addition a NDR feature. Biologically inspired models, such as the FHN model, and electrochemical models, often conceptualize oscillatory dynamics in terms of two interacting variables: an activator and an inhibitor. The activator promotes activity through positive feedback by the negative

Figure 2

Impedance spectroscopy, relaxation time and synaptic behavior of a fluidic nanochannel. **(a)** The impedance spectra show two arcs at negative voltages. At positive voltages (0.2–0.4 V) the spectra show chemical inductor impedance. The spectra are well described by the upper part of the equivalent circuit **(b)**: The element g_s is a series resistance, g_b is a parallel resistance, the elements (g_a, L_a) form the chemical inductor, and the capacitor C_m (“membrane” capacitance) gives the high frequency arc. The voltage V_{app} denotes the stationary voltage at which the impedance is measured by a superimposed small ac voltage. At positive potential (g_a, L_a) are positive, and they generate the inductive arc. At negative potential both (g_b, L_a) < 0, as shown in **(c, e)**. These negative values, when combined, generate a positive and stable capacitor response. At large potential $V = 2.0 - 3.6$ V an additional curling is observed at low frequency (inset of **(a)**), which is explained by additional polarization effect described by the branch (g_i, C_i) in **(b)**. From the impedance data, the relaxation time of the chemical inductor, Eq. [2], is obtained as $\tau_k = g_a L_a$, as shown in **(d)**. The τ_k is positive in both domains of positive and negative components, indicating a stable system. From the relaxation time the synapse learning properties can be fully described in **(f)**. The model [1,2] also gives insight to the evolution of the conductance activation variable x during potentiation and depression, **(g)**. Adapted from Ref. [33] Rivera-Sierra G, Ramirez P, Bisquet J, Bou A., J Am Chem Soc. 2025; 147:17,529–38, licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

Figure 3

Oscillation and impedance spectra of FitzHugh-Nagumo model. **(a)** Electrical representation: u voltage; I_0 input current; $x = i_L$ current in the inductor; $I_g(u)$ variable resistor; C_0 capacitance; R_a resistor; L_a inductor. **(b)** Small signal AC impedance model. **(c)** $u - I_0$ plane. The green line is the fast component of the current, and the pink line is the slow one. When added they give the blue line that is the stationary in the $I_0 - u$ characteristic. The blue point is the steady-state point at the nominal potential ($u_{app} = 0.7$) and the orange line is the corresponding constant current $I_0 = 0.509$ A. The red points are the Hopf bifurcations at $u_B = \pm 0.836$ V. **(d)** Limit cycle oscillation at constant current $I_0 = 0.509$ A. The green line is the nullcline $\dot{u} = 0$, and the pink line is the nullcline $\dot{x} = 0$. Trajectories and vector velocities are shown. The orange point is the starting condition. Color streamlines indicate the norm of the phase space velocity vector field. Parameters: $R_0 = 0.5 \Omega$; $R_a = 0.417 \Omega$; $\tau_0 = 0.01$ s; $\epsilon = 0.4$. **(e, f)** Impedance spectra for $R_1 = 0$, $C_0 = 1$ F, and other parameters as indicated (R in Ω , L_a in H). The point is the DC value $Z(\omega = 0)$, and the arrow indicates the direction of increasing frequency. **(e)** is the response of a chemical inductor providing damped oscillation towards the equilibrium point, **(f)** contains a negative resistance at finite frequencies indicating limit cycle oscillations.

resistance, while the inhibitor introduces negative feedback to regulate and suppress it. The dynamic interplay between these forces gives rise to cyclical patterns of excitation and inhibition, producing sustained rhythmic activity.

For example, the FHN model shown in Figure 3 can be expressed by the equations

$$I_0 = C_0 \frac{du}{dt} - \frac{1}{R_0} \left(u - \frac{u^3}{3} \right) + x \quad (3)$$

$$\tau_L \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{1}{R_a} u - x \quad (4)$$

The negative resistance is caused by the nonlinear cubic term in Eq [3], represented by the green box in Fig. 3a, and the x slow variable is the current in the inductor. Note that the impedance elements in the FHN represent circuit elements without direct electrochemical meaning, as it is a gross simplification of the HH model. The principles of oscillators based on IS response, though, can be applied to many classes of electrochemical oscillators [13,14,18,62,63].

The behavior of self-sustained oscillators is typically analyzed through the lens of nonlinear dynamical systems theory, particularly using the concept of bifurcations [64]. A key example is the Hopf bifurcation, which describes the transition from a stable fixed point to a stable periodic orbit (limit cycle) as a system parameter crosses a critical threshold. This transition marks the emergence of autonomous oscillations, with all trajectories converging to the limit cycle regardless of initial conditions, Fig. 3d. The system's stability can be assessed by examining the eigenvalues of the linearized differential equations. There is a deep connection between autonomous oscillatory behavior and the system's response to external periodic forcing, as revealed through IS [1,65]. The impedance spectrum not only provides criteria for temporal stability but can also signal the onset of a Hopf bifurcation.

Although electrochemical self-sustained oscillators have been extensively studied throughout the past century [62,63], the translation of oscillatory conditions into the language of the Nyquist stability criterion was notably advanced by the work of Koper and collaborators [13,14]. These papers provide a detailed characterization of the impedance spectra related to bifurcation and self-oscillation, and the method has been used extensively [15,16,66]. The relevant transition of spectra from stationary to limit cycle oscillation is shown in Fig. 3 (e, f). The impedance response of the HH neuron model has been extensively studied. It is characterized by the presence of three chemical inductors [34,67–69].

Although linearized analysis provides valuable insight into nonlinear dynamical systems, it often falls short in fully capturing the formation of limit cycles and other complex trajectories in phase space. Limit cycles,

particularly those arising around stable equilibria or near bifurcation points, tend to extend far beyond the local neighborhood of the equilibrium, highlighting the intrinsically global nature of such dynamics. This is observed in the sensitivity of phase orbits to initial parameters in a saddle-node bifurcation [70]. To address these challenges, frequency-domain methods for identifying nonlinear components [71–73] offer powerful tools for advancing the understanding of these behaviors.

Detailed conductance-based nonlinear neuron models, often incorporating thousands of synapses, are essential for understanding the computational properties of individual neurons and large-scale neuronal networks, as well as for interpreting experimental data. However, applying impedance-based analysis to such complex, interconnected networks remains a largely unexplored challenge. Impedance offers a powerful framework for simplifying these detailed models while preserving their core computational characteristics. By maintaining the transfer impedance between synapses and the soma, the approach described in Ref. [74] enables the construction of reduced models that accurately replicate the input–output behavior of the originals. This allows for the merging of synapses with identical impedance profiles, dramatically decreasing the number of compartments and computational load, paving the way for more practical and scalable simulations of biologically realistic neural networks.

Discussion

The methodologies of IS have emerged as a versatile and indispensable tool for probing neuromorphic materials and systems. By deconvoluting resistive, capacitive, and diffusive contributions across a broad frequency range, IS enables direct insights into the interplay between ionic transport, interfacial charge accumulation, and electronic conduction that underlie synaptic plasticity. In electrolyte-gated devices, it serves to unravel volumetric doping and capacitive coupling mechanisms that dictate device response, while in MOF- and polymer-based synaptic systems it clarifies ion migration pathways and dielectric relaxation processes that mimic biological learning and memory. Beyond material characterization, impedance analysis also provides design guidelines for tailoring switching speed, energy efficiency, and stability in artificial synapses. As neuromorphic engineering increasingly integrates diverse material platforms, IS stands not only as a diagnostic method but also as a predictive framework that bridges microscopic transport phenomena with macroscopic device function, paving the way for the rational design of next-generation bioinspired computing systems.

In the context of neuromorphic synapses, the crucial property is the conductance change, or resistive switching. IS provides a frequency-resolved fingerprint of the dynamic balance between ionic migration and electronic transport, thereby linking microscopic transport events to macroscopic conductance modulation. It reveals inductive features associated with potentiation processes and capacitive elements corresponding to depression, offering a powerful means to disentangle the mechanisms underpinning long-term potentiation and long-term depression. More broadly, impedance-based analysis has proven valuable for quantifying plasticity timescales and guiding the rational design of memristive devices with tailored switching kinetics and stability for neuromorphic hardware.

A parallel line of research concerns self-sustained oscillators that play the role of neuron elements and enable OBC. Electrochemical oscillators have been widely studied, and their description through the Nyquist stability criterion has provided a detailed characterization of the impedance spectra associated with bifurcation and self-oscillation. In this context, IS allows one to monitor in real time the transition of the impedance response from stationary states, characterized by stable semicircles, to limit-cycle oscillations, where negative resistance or inductive loops dominate the complex impedance plane. The impedance response of neuron models, such as the HH framework, is also characterized by the presence of distinct inductive features that reflect the interplay of ion channel kinetics in generating rhythmic spiking. By bridging electrochemical oscillators with neuron models, IS provides a unifying framework to describe both artificial and biological self-sustained oscillations, enabling predictive control of oscillatory neuromorphic systems.

Conclusion

In conclusion, physics-based computational networks—whether based on neuromorphic spiking neurons or driven by oscillatory dynamics—mark a transformative step toward physically embodied, energy-efficient computation that mirrors the fundamental principles of biological intelligence. By overcoming the limitations of traditional architectures, neuromorphic systems bring us closer to building machines that perceive, learn, and adapt in brain-like ways. Within this context, IS emerges as a promising analytical tool, offering deep insight into the dynamic behavior of neuromorphic elements. While its use has been largely confined to electrochemical oscillators and memristive systems, its potential for broader application in characterizing complex neuromorphic components is clear. Expanding its use could significantly enhance our ability

to design and optimize next-generation brain-inspired technologies.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used chatGPT4 in order to improve the writing and clarify explanations. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by the European Research Council (ERC) via Horizon Europe Advanced Grant, grant agreement n° 101097688 (“PeroSpiker”).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coelec.2025.101767>.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

Papers of particular interest, published within the period of review, have been highlighted as:

- * of special interest
- ** of outstanding interest

1. Vivier V, Orazem ME: **Impedance analysis of electrochemical systems**. *Chem Rev* 2022, **122**:11131–68.
Excellent review on impedance spectroscopy that establishes a physical analysis of stability conditions in equivalent circuits.
2. Pandey SV, Prochowicz D, Mahapatra A, Pandiaraj S, Alodhayb A, Akin S, et al.: **The circuitry landscape of perovskite solar cells: an in-depth analysis**. *J Energy Chem* 2024, **94**:393–413.
3. Mehonic A, Ielmini D, Roy K, Mutlu O, Kvatinsky S, Serrano-Gotarredona T, et al.: **Roadmap to neuromorphic computing with emerging technologies**. *APL Mater* 2024, **12**, 109201.
4. Duan X, Cao Z, Gao K, Yan W, Sun S, Zhou G, et al.: **Memristor-based neuromorphic chips**. *Adv Mater* 2024, **36**, 2310704.
5. Sun B, Ranjan S, Zhou G, Guo T, Xia Y, Wei L, et al.: **Multistate resistive switching behaviors for neuromorphic computing in memristor**. *Materials Today Advances* 2021, **9**, 100125.
6. Hutcheon B, Yarom Y: **Resonance, oscillation and the intrinsic frequency preferences of neurons**. *Trends Neurosci* 2000, **23**: 216–222.
7. Zhu J, Zhang T, Yang Y, Huang R: **A comprehensive review on emerging artificial neuromorphic devices**. *Appl Phys Rev* 2020, **7**, 011312.
8. Harikesh PC, Tu D, Fabiano S: **Organic electrochemical neurons for neuromorphic perception**. *Nat Electron* 2024, **7**: 525–536.
9. He H-K, Huang H-M, Yang R: **Two-terminal neuromorphic memristors**. *Neuromorp Device Brain-Inspired Comp* 2022: 1–46.
10. Song M-K, Kang J-H, Zhang X, Ji W, Ascoli A, Messaris I, et al.: **Recent advances and future prospects for memristive materials, devices, and systems**. *ACS Nano* 2023, **17**: 11994–12039.
11. Jenkins A: **Self-oscillation**. *Phys Rep* 2013, **525**:167–222.
12. Stiefel KM, Ermentrout GB: **Neurons as oscillators**. *J Neurophysiol* 2016, **116**:2950–2960.
13. Koper M TM: **Non-linear phenomena in electrochemical systems**. *J Chem Soc, Faraday Trans* 1998, **94**:1369–1378.
14. Koper MTM: **Oscillations and complex dynamical bifurcations in electrochemical systems**. *Adv Chem Phys* 1996, **92**:161.
15. Naito M, Tanaka N, Okamoto H: **General relationship between complex impedance and linear stability in electrochemical systems**. *J Chem Phys* 1999, **111**:9908–9917.
16. Sadkowski A, Dolata M, Diard JP: **Kramers-kronig transforms as validation of electrochemical impedance data near discontinuity**. *J Electrochem Soc* 2004, **151**, E20.
17. Bisquert J: **Hopf bifurcations in electrochemical, neuronal, and semiconductor systems analysis by impedance spectroscopy**. *Appl Phys Rev* 2022, **9**, 011318.
18. Bisquert J. *Device physics recipe to make spiking neurons* ****** *chemical physics reviews*, **4**; 2023, 031313.
Establishes the general trends of impedance analysis of N-type of neuron-like oscillatory models.
19. Zhang Q, Liu X, Yin L, Chen P, Wang Y, Yan T: **Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy on the capacitance of ionic liquid–acetonitrile electrolytes**. *Electrochim Acta* 2018, **270**: 352–362.
20. Elliott JD, Papaderakis AA, Dryfe RAW, Carbone P: **The electrochemical double layer at the graphene/aqueous electrolyte interface: what we can learn from simulations, experiments, and theory**. *J Math Chem C* 2022, **10**: 15225–15262.
21. Torricelli F, Adrahtas DZ, Bao Z, Berggren M, Biscarini F, Bonfiglio A, et al.: **Electrolyte-gated transistors for enhanced performance bioelectronics**. *Nat Rev Methods Primers* 2021, **1**:66.
22. Zhang H, Rivera-Sierra G, Siahjani-Gultekin S, Rubio-Magnieto J, Allagui A, Sanjuán I, et al.: **Transient charging of mixed ionic-electronic conductors by anomalous diffusion**. *Adv Mater* 2025, e07739.
23. Friedlein JT, McLeod RR, Rivnay J: **Device physics of organic electrochemical transistors**. *Org Electron* 2018, **63**:398–414.
24. Bisquert J, Keene ST: **Using the transversal admittance to understand organic electrochemical transistors**. *Adv Sci* 2025, **12**, 2410393.
25. Kim S, Kwon O, Kim S, Jang S, Yu S, Lee CH, et al.: **Modulating synaptic plasticity with metal–organic framework for information-filterable artificial retina**. *Nat Commun* 2025, **16**: 162.
26. Yao Z, Pan L, Liu L, Zhang J, Lin Q, Ye Y, et al. Simultaneous implementation of resistive switching and rectifying effects in a metal-organic framework with switched hydrogen bond pathway. *Sci Adv*.5:eaaw4515.
27. Gonzales C, Bou A, Guerrero A, Bisquert J: **Capacitive and inductive characteristics of volatile perovskite resistive switching devices with analog memory**. *J Phys Chem Lett* 2024, **15**:6496–6503.
28. Pendyala N-K, Gonzales C, Guerrero A: **Decoupling volatile and nonvolatile response in reliable halide perovskite memristors**. *Small Struct* 2024, **6**, 2400380.

Explaining synaptic properties of halide perovskite memristors based on inductive and capacitive components.

29. Law CS, Wang J, Nielsch K, Abell AD, Bisquert J, Santos A: **Recent advances in fluidic neuromorphic computing.** *Appl Phys Rev* 2025, **12**, 021309.
 30. Ramirez P, Gomez V, Cervera J, Mafe S, Bisquert J: **Synaptical tunability of multipore nanofluidic memristors.** *J Phys Chem Lett* 2023, **14**:10930–10934.
 31. Wang D, Kvetny M, Liu J, Brown W, Li Y, Wang G: **Transmembrane potential across single conical nanopores and resulting memristive and memcapacitive ion transport.** *J Am Chem Soc* 2012, **134**:3651–3654.
 32. Ramirez P, Cervera J, Nasir S, Ali M, Ensinger W, Mafe S: **Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy of membranes with nanofluidic conical pores.** *J Colloid Interface Sci* 2024, **655**:876–885.
- Experimental demonstration of the capacitive and inductive impedances of a nanofluidic memristor.
33. Rivera-Sierra G, Ramirez P, Bisquert J, Bou A: **Relaxation time of multipore nanofluidic memristors for neuromorphic applications.** *J Am Chem Soc* 2025, **147**:17529–17538.
 34. Bou A, Bisquert J: **Impedance spectroscopy dynamics of biological neural elements: from memristors to neurons and synapses.** *J Phys Chem B* 2021, **125**:9934–9949.
 35. Minnekhanov AA, Shvetsov BS, Martyshov MM, Nikiryu KE, Kukueva EV, Presnyakov MY, et al.: **On the resistive switching mechanism of parylene-based memristive devices.** *Org Electron* 2019, **74**:89–95.
 36. Yadav D, Levenne H, Stathopoulos S, Ramesh R, Kumar S, Prodromakis T: **Impedance spectroscopy of hafnium oxide: memristive and memcapacitive switching with annealing.** *IEEE Trans Electron Dev* 2025, **72**:2271–2277.
 37. Ko J, Ock C, Gim H, Hong K, Lee Y, Kwon KC: **Two-dimensional materials for artificial sensory devices: advancing neuromorphic sensing technology.** *npj 2D Materials and Applications* 2025, **9**:35.
 38. Fukushima T, Maeda K, Yoshimura T, Ashida A, Fujimura N: **Impedance analysis of controlled-polarization-type ferroelectric-gate thin film transistor using resistor–capacitor lumped constant circuit.** *Jpn J Appl Phys* 2011, **50**, 04DD16.
 39. Todri-Sanial A, Delacour C, Abernot M, Sabo F: **Computing with oscillators from theoretical underpinnings to applications and demonstrators.** *npj Unconv Comput* 2024, **1**:14.
 40. Kiss IZ, Zhai Y, Hudson JL: **Emerging coherence in a population of chemical oscillators.** *Science*. 2002, **296**:1676–1678.
 41. Nijholt E, Ocampo-Espindola JL, Eroglu D, Kiss IZ, Pereira T: **Emergent hypernetworks in weakly coupled oscillators.** *Nat Commun* 2022, **13**:4849.
 42. Rotstein HG: **Preferred frequency responses to oscillatory inputs in an electrochemical cell model: Linear amplitude and phase resonance.** *Phys Rev* 2013, **88**, 062913.
 43. Izhikevich EM: *Dynamical systems in neuroscience*. MIT Press; 2007.
 44. Brown P: **Oscillatory nature of human basal ganglia activity: relationship to the pathophysiology of parkinson's disease.** *Mov Disord* 2003, **18**:357–363.
 45. Zhang Y, Wang Z, Zhu J, Yang Y, Rao M, Song W, et al.: **Brain-inspired computing with memristors: challenges in devices, circuits, and systems.** *Appl Phys Rev* 2020, **7**, 011308.
 46. Kim S-Y, Zhang H, Rivera-Sierra G, Fenollosa R, Rubio-Magnieto J, Bisquert J: **Introduction to neuromorphic functions of memristors: the inductive nature of synapse potentiation.** *J Appl Phys* 2025, **137**, 111101.
 47. Bisquert J, Shim W, Kim S-Y, Linares-Barranco B: **Synaptic function in memristor devices for neuromorphic circuit applications.** *Adv Electron Mater* 2025, 202400903.
- Recent survey of conductance-activated synaptic systems.
48. Bisquert J: **Hysteresis, rectification and relaxation times of nanofluidic pores for neuromorphic circuit applications.** *Advan Phy Res* 2024, **3**, 2400029.
 49. Bisquert J: **Inductive and capacitive hysteresis of current-voltage curves. A unified structural dynamics in solar energy devices, memristors, ionic transistors and bioelectronics.** *PRX Energy* 2023, **3**, 011001.
 50. Bisquert J, Guerrero A: **Chemical inductor.** *J Am Chem Soc* 2022, **144**:5996–6009.
 51. Ramirez P, Portillo S, Cervera J, Bisquert J, Mafe S: **Memristive arrangements of nanofluidic pores.** *Phys Rev* 2024, **109**, 044803.
 52. Brinker D, Hensle N, Horstmann de la Viña J, Franzetti I, Bühre LV, Andaluri UA, et al.: **Inductive loops in impedance spectra of PEM water electrolyzers.** *J Power Sources* 2024, **622**, 235375.
 53. Armstrong RD, Henderson M: **Impedance plane display of a reaction with an absorbed intermediate.** *J Electroanal Chem* 1972, **39**:81.
 54. Akabuogu EU, Zhang L, Krašovec R, Roberts IS, Waigh TA: **Electrical impedance spectroscopy with bacterial biofilms: neuronal-like behavior.** *Nano Lett* 2024, **24**:2234–2241.
- Report of inductive behaviour of *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) biofilms measured by impedance spectroscopy.
55. Aranda CA, Li W, Martínez-Ferrero E, Pistor P, Oskam G, Palomares E, et al.: **Insights from impedance spectroscopy in perovskite solar cells with self-assembled monolayers: decoding SAM's tricks.** *J Phys Chem Lett* 2025, **16**:2301–2308.
 56. Zelić K, Mele I, Bhowmik A, Katrašnik T: **Phase separating electrode materials - chemical inductors?** *Energy Storage Mater* 2023, **56**:489–494.
 57. Yadav D, Gora S, Kumar A, Jangra M, Yadav KL, Datta A, et al.: **Probing the photo-activated switching dynamics of halide perovskite memristors.** *ACS Appl Electron Mater* 2023, **5**:3765–3771.
 58. Liu S, Guan J, Yin L, Zhou L, Huang J, Mu Y, et al.: **Solution-processed synaptic memristors based on halide perovskite nanocrystals.** *J Phys Chem Lett* 2022, **13**:10994–11000.
 59. Dhifaoui H, Hemasiri NH, Mehdi H, Bouazizi A, Kazim S, Ahmad S: **Impact of polymeric hole-selective layers on chemical inductance in inverted perovskite solar cells.** *Energy Technol* 2022, **10**, 2200624.
 60. Bisquert J, Miranda E, Roldan JB: **Hysteresis in memristors produces a conduction inductance and a conduction capacitance effects.** *PhysChemChemPhys*. 2024, **26**:13804–13813.
 61. Hodgkin AL, Huxley AF: **A quantitative description of membrane current and its application to conduction and excitation in nerve.** *J Physiol*. 1952, **117**:500–544.
 62. Orlik M: *Self-organization in electrochemical systems I*. Springer; 2012.
 63. Krischer K: **Nonlinear dynamics in electrochemical systems.** In Alkire RC, Kolb DM. *Advances in electrochemical science and engineering*, **8**. Wiley; 2002:89–208.

64. Strogatz SH: *Nonlinear dynamics and chaos*. 2nd ed. CRC Press; 2019.
65. Bisquert J: **Negative inductor effects in nonlinear two-dimensional systems. Oscillatory neurons and memristors.** *Chem Phys Rev* 2022, **3**, 041305.
66. Ascoli A, Demirkol AS, Tetzlaff R, Slesazek S, Mikolajick T, Chua LO: **On local activity and edge of chaos in a NaMLab memristor.** *Front Neurosci* 2021, **15**, 651452.
67. Cole KS: *Membranes, ions and impulses. A chapter of classical biophysics*. University of California Press; 1968.
68. Chua L, Sbitnev V, Kim H: **Neurons are poised near the edge of chaos.** *Intern J Bifurcation Chaos* 2012, **22**, 1250098.
69. Ascoli A, Demirkol AS, Messaris I, Ntinis V, Prousalis D, Slesazek S, *et al.*: **Edge of chaos theory unveils the first and simplest ever reported hodgkin–huxley neuristor.** *Adv Electron Mater* 2025, **11**, 2400789.
70. Koper MTM: **Bifurcations of mixed-mode oscillations in a three-variable autonomous Van der Pol-Duffing model with a cross-shaped phase diagram.** *Phys Nonlinear Phenom* 1995, **80**:72–94.
71. Lopez-Richard V, Pradhan S, Wengenroth Silva RS, Lipan O, Castelano LK, Höfling S, *et al.*: **Beyond equivalent circuit representations in nonlinear systems with inherent memory.** *J Appl Phys* 2024, **136**, 165103.
Interesting study of the nonlinear effects of measurements in the frequency domain.
72. Yarragolla S, Hemke T, Jalled F, Gergs T, Trieschmann J, Arul T, *et al.*: **Identifying and understanding the nonlinear behavior of memristive devices.** *Sci Rep* 2024, **14**, 31633.
73. Hernández S, Suárez A: **Systematic methodology for the global stability analysis of nonlinear circuits.** *IEEE Trans Microw Theor Tech* 2019, **67**:3–15.
74. Amsalem O, Eyal G, Rogozinski N, Gevaert M, Kumbhar P, Schürmann F, *et al.*: **An efficient analytical reduction of detailed nonlinear neuron models.** *Nat Commun* 2020, **11**: 288.
Reduction of impedances applied to nonlinear neuron models consisting of thousands of synapses.